

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES GUIDING THE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM AND OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL IN TERMS OF MORAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

We can always say, of course, that the great role and opportunities of extracurricular activities in the development of schoolchildren as individuals, in the spiritual, moral, aesthetic, art and sports education of students are high. In extracurricular activities, students' knowledge and literacy levels are significantly activated, their creative abilities are significantly increased, on this basis, their talents and abilities are revealed, and they also create fully favorable opportunities and conditions for their future professional choices, their spiritual and moral qualities, especially their scientific outlook, aesthetics. and artistic-literary, develops speech culture, cultivates deep interest and strong love and strong inclination to knowledge. Outside the classroom, outside the class and outside the school In order to organize educational activities and achieve successful results, in addition to being guided by the generally defined and accepted didactic principles of the educational process, the unique didactic and scientific-pedagogical principles of the organization of such events and the pedagogical guidance of these events must also be followed constantly and regularly. should be done.

Keywords: education, teaching, pedagogy, principle.

Introduction

In the decree of the President of the country, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, on the State Strategy for the Development of Education (Education Strategy) in the Republic of Azerbaijan, it was specially mentioned that the implementation of stimulation mechanisms in improving the quality of education was given a wide place.

Thus, the quality of education depends on both the academic knowledge of students and the training of competent teaching staff, their use of new pedagogical technologies, innovative methods, which is stated in the strategy that in order to further improve the quality, stimulation and encouragement mechanisms should be used constantly, in the education system, issues related to the creation and application of the system of grants that stimulate innovative activity of new pedagogical technologies should be given wide attention and their real implementation in the pedagogical process should be ensured.

Extracurricular and extracurricular activities have an important role and importance among the stimulating mechanisms affecting the special quality of education in extracurricular activities.

Activities outside the classroom can be said to be an indisputably necessary component of the multi-faceted educational activities of the school.

These activities are usually organized either before the lesson (if the lessons are held in the second shift), or after the lesson (if the lessons are held in the first shift), or by teachers who are members of the pedagogical team, school leaders, class leaders, various types of student self-government bodies, and leaders of children and youth organizations. can be successfully implemented.

In educational activities outside the classroom, students more freely and voluntarily participate in various cognitive, moral and ethical pedagogical processes, work on various teaching and learning materials, conduct experiments, go on excursions and walks, hold meetings, debates and discussions, sports events,

competitions, participates in art events, and as a result, we can say that student achievement increases, their academic and scientific knowledge increases, students' knowledge and outlook expands, their potential opportunities and abilities, talents and skills develop.

Analysis

It is also of great and special importance to always strictly follow the didactic and scientific-pedagogical principles established in determining the correct organization of extracurricular and extracurricular educational activities outside the classroom, the content, forms, and effective methods and means of educational activities.

We can note that the classification of pedagogical principles and their quantity have not reached a unanimous opinion among educators. Nevertheless, we can interpret the classification of generally accepted principles, which can be guided in the organization of extracurricular and extracurricular activities. They are as follows:

1. The principle of humanism
2. The principle of democracy
3. The principle of equality
4. The principle of personal orientation
5. The principle of student orientation
6. The principle of result orientation
6. The principle of integrability
7. Voluntary principle
8. The principle of consideration of individual qualities, interests and talents and abilities
9. The principle of continuity, consistency and systematicity
10. The principle of high activity and awareness
11. The principle of interactivity.
12. Principle of activity
13. The principle of cooperation (2)

The above mentioned principles can be considered as common pedagogical principles.

Despite all this, extracurricular and extracurricular activities have their own characteristics.

We can group and interpret those principles as follows:

1. The principle of interesting organization of out-of-school and out-of-class events and organization according to children's interest and inclination.

Events organized according to this principle are supposed to be interesting. If the events are organized interestingly and the students participate in the events with interest, of course extracurricular activities will be attractive and important.

In this regard, teachers and tutors should always study the interests, inclinations and passions, needs, and individual psychological characteristics of schoolchildren and, accordingly, direct them to extracurricular activities and educational activities.

2. We can mention the second of the principles, compliance with the principle of constancy in the conduct of events.

As the name suggests, the organized events must be voluntary in nature. Forced and uninterested measures should not be allowed.

Schoolchildren should be happy and comfortable in events. Freedom should be allowed.

These are considered the natural rights of children. They cannot be forced to take any action.

For this, it is necessary to learn the interest and ability of children's psychology.

Every pedagogue, teacher and educator should be deeply familiar with child psychology and should be guided by it.

3. We can say that the third of the principles is that the events are public in nature. In other words, organized extracurricular and extracurricular events should be of social importance.

It should be organized for the benefit of society. With this, we can say that social consciousness should be formed in schoolchildren.

Only then the measures can be important and useful.

The principle we have mentioned also requires that associations, clubs, museum works, etc. organized in the school. to be organized in a public manner.

Social awareness and social thinking should be formed in the work being carried out.

4. The fourth of the mentioned principles is the principle of initiative and activity in the organization of events.

The requirement of this principle is that children, teenagers and young people should be active and take the initiative in the events.

Teachers and educators should also try to ensure the activity and initiative of schoolchildren while organizing the events. (1)

Only the events held in conditions of activity and initiative will be important and useful.

5. The fifth of the mentioned principles is the principle of using game elements, romance, and emotional situations in holding the events we call.

This principle requires consideration of children's nature.

Child nature loves play, loves romance, loves emotions.

From this point of view, it is necessary to give a

wide place to emotions and game elements in the organization of events. Children must play.

A child who does not play cannot develop.

Play develops children comprehensively.

It develops their speech, thinking, intelligence.

This principle also requires that the events should not be boring or boring. Let it be organized cheerfully and actively.

6. Among the mentioned principles is the principle of connecting the events with life, construction works, and practical works. (3)

The requirement of this principle is that the organized events combine the unity of theory and practice.

The events should be connected with life, connected with practical, daily tasks.

We can also mention here that the theories that are combined with practical work are more qualitative and long-term.

Also, the impact of the event is higher and will not be forgotten for a long time.

Such a principle also requires that the works carried out are organized in connection with the construction works of the society.

The idea of the principle requires that students apply the knowledge gained in the learning process in practice and further strengthen it.

7. The seventh established principle is the principle of creating favorable, comfortable, suitable, fertile conditions in the organization of out-of-class and out-of-school events, which is considered an important principle.

Here, it is required to create favorable conditions for the events, to create fertile conditions for the activities of children, teenagers and young people, to create a favorable climate, conditions and fertile ground for the events.

Only if this is the case, the actions will be useful and effective. The event is also important.

Otherwise, the measure will be useless and ineffective, and will have a formal character.

8. The eighth principle identified is the use of technology in extracurricular and extracurricular activities.

It is the principle of using technical means, innovations, new pedagogical technologies.

As the name suggests, this principle requires the use of technical means in the events.

The use of technical means makes the event more qualitative and interesting.

Our time is the age of technology, the age of technologies. From this point of view, the application of innovations and the application of new technologies should be given a lot of space in the organization of extracurricular activities. (2)

Here, of course, the use of active and interactive methods is of great importance.

In non-school educational institutions and in regular and regular events, computer equipment should be given ample space.

Using computer technology, various multimedia, audio-visuals during various meetings, conversations, walks can be the basis for better organization, efficient and quality organization and useful construction of the event.

9. The identified ninth pedagogical principle requires that children, teenagers and young people be involved in various interesting activities, taking into account their individual characteristics, psychological characteristics, as well as talents and abilities.

The essence of this principle requires that teachers and educators, with the skill of a psychologist, study well the individual types and psychological physiological characteristics, types, and characteristics of children, teenagers and young people.

You can't organize things without knowing all this.

Each of them has its own interest, its own world, its own interests and inclinations.

Teachers and educators should know all these things better, learn them and always follow them in the organization of events.

Here it is required that the special abilities, potential opportunities, talents, abilities and skills of every child, teenager and young person be taken into account with special attention and sensitivity, and interesting activities and events should be organized accordingly.

10. The tenth principle established is that there should be uniform demands in the conduct of events, and at the same time, the principle of always respecting the personality of the student is envisaged.

This is a humane principle. Great educator Makarenko brought this to our pedagogical science.

He said that it is necessary to respect the child's personality as much as possible and to demand as much as possible.

As a pedagogical principle, this principle has been accepted as a general principle in many fields. As the name suggests, the essence of this principle is that students should be treated with respect and demand.

It is important to give them special care, attention and respect.

Also, the requirements of children, adolescents and young people should be respected and coordinated.

In other words, it is necessary to respect children and make strict demands on them.

The outstanding Ukrainian educator AS Makarenko skillfully used the aforementioned principle in his pedagogical activity, he re-educated, brought back to life, and brought up worthy citizens of society.

He proudly said that if they ask me, what is the main thing in your work experience?

I would say then that you should always respect people as much as you can, always treat them with care and then make as many demands as you can.

11. The eleventh principle determined is the principle of taking into account the gender differences of children, teenagers and young people in conducting events. (5)

This stated principle requires that there are measures and exercises where gender differences should be taken into account.

There are some associations where gender differences - boys and girls - should be taken into account.

This may include various sports associations and clubs.

12. Again, we can say that the twelfth established principle is to take into account the age of students,

schoolchildren, their anatomy and physiology in the organization and conduct of events.

Children's health is also taken into account here. Measures should be planned according to their health.

Of course, the measures should have a positive effect on the health of schoolchildren.

In the organization and conduct of events, educators must take into account the age levels and psychological characteristics of the students and always do things accordingly.

Therefore, in the organization of events, children's age characteristics and individual psychological characteristics should always be taken seriously, and actions, plans, and projects should be implemented accordingly.

13. In out-of-class and out-of-school work - if we have to interpret it as the thirteenth principle, we can say that in general, complex actions should be preferred.

In other words, various active and interactive methods of education and training, problem situation methods should be used in conducting events and they should always be used skillfully and creatively.

14. In out-of-class and out-of-school activities - we can mention this principle as the fourteenth principle, where special attention should be paid to the creative products of students and they should be valued and used as a stimulating principle.

The law on education and the strategy also indicate that stimulating measures are not used as a principle in the educational process.

What is the importance of effective stimulation in improving the quality of education?

We can note that students in secondary schools can always receive various stimulating awards for their academic success, for their participation and victories in education, creative competitions, sports, as well as for their socially useful activities, excellent education, Olympiads, competitions and competitions.

Among these awards, students are extremely happy, they create positive motivation for education, science, and gain deep knowledge in children, and they have effective stimulating effects.

The school environment should continuously encourage and stimulate the students.

A system of stimulating measures at school is constantly necessary to provide a favorable environment for schoolchildren, to increase the level of motivation and to show a more responsible attitude to student duties.

Different types of awards are presented to students who are selected for their knowledge and skills and their achievements in the school.

These award types include:

1. Declaration of thanksgiving.
2. Awarding of honorary diplomas.
3. Submission of acknowledgments
4. Awarding parents with letters of thanks
5. Presentation of gold or silver medals
6. Rewarding with a valuable gift
7. Issuance of scholarship payment.
8. Submission of certificates of distinction

9. Placing information on the permanent official website of educational organizers on the Internet

10. Dissemination of information about the success of students in the media, newspapers and magazines, in the press.

11. Sending as a representative to various honorary events, congresses, conferences.

12. Awarding valuable teaching materials.

In addition, in accordance with the provisions on competitions held in schools, subject olympiads and competitions, stimulating means are applied and announced to the school's pedagogical and student staff.

Encouragement is applied in the context of wide publicity, it is brought to the attention of students, parents, school employees, it is constantly published in the school press, on the school's website. (2)

Letters of thanks to the student's family, letters of thanks to the workplace of his parents, letters of thanks to the teachers, class leaders, tutors who helped the student to achieve a positive result can also be sent as stimulating measures.

Stimulating factors and motivational methods should be decided by the school director at the meetings of the pedagogical council and should be applied with the recommendation of the class teacher.

15. As the fifteenth principle, we can say that out-of-class and out-of-school training, education and educational work requires that out-of-class and out-of-school educational work be regularly and constantly reconciled with the general training and education of the class and school, as well as educational work.

Their work should never repeat each other, and actions should be directed and directed to the improvement of the quality of education and educational work of the school, the class, the development of schoolchildren's scientific worldview, critical and logical thinking and thinking.

Activities outside the classroom and outside the school should not hinder the education of children, teenagers and young people, on the contrary, it should serve to improve and further develop it.

We can say that out-of-class and out-of-school activities are another form of continuation of the training activities that are constantly held at school.

16. In the training process, the principle of applying and strengthening the knowledge acquired by the students in the classroom and extracurricular activities.

This principle requires that the acquired knowledge and experience be constantly applied in practical work.

The application of practical work will further help to acquire knowledge more firmly and develop a scientific outlook.

17. The principle of humanism is always fulfilled in the regular organization of activities and events outside the classroom and outside the school.

This is great humanity and respect for man and immense care and compassion for man.

18. In education outside the classroom and outside the school, we can say that the principles of democracy must be followed constantly and regularly.

Democracy means respecting human rights, including the rights of students, ensuring their free and independent activities.

19. As the nineteenth principle, we can say that the equality of children, teenagers and young people is not ensured when organizing events and activities outside the classroom and outside the school.

That is, students have equal rights.

They cannot be separated.

They cannot be divided into good students, poor students, disciplined or undisciplined groups.

Or they cannot be separated or divided into groups according to their social origin, religious belief, or the status of their parents. That is why we say that all children have equal rights.

Their equality must be ensured constantly and regularly.

20. As the twentieth principle, we can say that one of the most important and important principles is the principle of considering their research skills and talents when organizing activities outside the classroom and outside the school in the pedagogical process.

Ensuring the continuity of education in the pandemic has become the main task of educators.

We can say that the coronavirus pandemic, which is completely covering the world today, has set a number of urgent tasks in front of the general education system, which has become practical issues today in the full provision of education, the ability to study independently, the use of ICT skills, virtual and distance education, and the application of the school project.

In order to ensure the continuity of the teaching process, there is ample space and opportunities for the use of various internet resources and tools (ZOOM, Microsoft Teams, Youtube, Skype, etc.) is asleep

In order to ensure the activity of students and to increase the effectiveness of their activities, various online competitions were held here.

We can say that the competition of virtual excellent students and advanced schoolchildren was the most relevant of these new types of online competitions.

Mutallibova Pari, a 6th-grade student of school No. 8 in Baku, was among the winners of this online competition.

Class leaders are very active in such interesting events held at the school.

Of course, all these activities are organized by class leaders. I got acquainted with the work of the class teachers here by accessing the website of this school through the Internet.

One of the interesting and important issues in the activity of class leaders is that there are important and necessary documents in their educational work folder.

Considering the importance of the documents, we considered it important to give the dissertation in our work.

The teacher of the school, Sevinj Aliyeva, considered it important and important to have the following documents in the folder presented by an advanced class teacher:

The following documents should be in the class teacher's educational work folder:

1. The annual action plan of the teacher in charge of the class.

This includes: annual plans, monthly and weekly plans

2. Permanent appointment book with parents.

Meetings with parents are recorded in this notebook.

3. Special passport of the class.

This document shows the name list of the students of the class, how many girls and boys there are, and their brief educational achievements.

4. All issues of the class wall newspaper

The class leader must collect, sew and keep all issues of the class wall newspaper.

5. Content notebook of individual conversations with students.

In this notebook, he writes down the contents and expresses his thoughts with any student, when and on what subject.

6. Plans of work with students with weak reading and results of executed documents.

This is one of the important documents. The head of the class should record the content of the individual work discussions with the students, especially with the weak students.

7. Notebook of work, conversations and relationships conducted by the head of the class with the teachers teaching in the class.

Class leaders should keep records of their activities, conversations and relationships with the teachers who teach in the class.

These should always be reflected in a special notebook and should be continued.

8. A book of continuous observations and interviews for the regular study of students.

Every school should have a book of continuous observations and interviews for the regular study of students and should be done regularly.

9. Continuous work plan of the class parent committee

The work plan of the class parent committee is one of the most important documents. This should be done continuously.

10. There is no permanent record book of the events, which includes reports, speech texts, scenarios.

11. Permanent protocol book of parent meetings.

This important document is one of the important and important documents that reflect the relations with the parents. This should be done continuously.

12. Minutes of student meetings.

This is considered one of the important documents. It must be written and carried out constantly.

13. Book of reflecting scenarios of moral conversations with students.

Each class should have a book of moral conversations with students, reports, scenarios, in which events held on significant days can be recorded.

14. Personal self-education plan and program

Each classroom teacher should have a personal self-education plan and program. Here it should be noted regularly which books he reads.

15. Guidebook of documents.

In this notebook, governing documents, decrees and decisions are recorded.

All these are important documents in the organization of out-of-class and out-of-school activities that every school should have and the above should be followed continuously.

The result

Many factors affect the quality of education in secondary schools, one of which is the organization of extracurricular activities.

Extracurricular activities are an integral part of the school's educational and educational work, which, with its unique specific organization rules, unique content, interesting work forms and methods, creates interest and love for knowledge in students, instills feelings of responsible attitude to education, increases students' knowledge and worldview, and encourages them to gain more knowledge. creates a strong stimulus.

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